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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE LAKE OF PILATUS IN AN ANTIQUE MANUSCRIPT: PIERRE BERSUIRE AND THE FOURTEENTH-CENTURY DARK RENOWN OF NORCIA'S LAKE¹

1. A benedictine monk, an Italian town, a sinister lake

«I heard a remarkable, horrific tale about Norcia, the Italian town, that was reported to me as an absolutely proven truth by a certain prelate, a trustworthy person indeed among all men» (in the original Latin text: «Exemplum terribile esse circa Norciam Italie civitatem audivi pro vero et pro centies experto narrari a quodam praelato summe inter alios fide digno»).

This is the opening remark of a stunning excerpt found in a precious fourteenth-century manuscript: the “Reductorium Morale” by Petrus Berchorius (Pierre Bersuire), a French benedictine monk and abbot, who lived between 1290 and 1362 and was a member of the papal court in Avignon, known for his erudition and his learned literary works.

It is the first time that one of the ancient manuscripts of the “Reductorium Morale”, containing a most remarkable quote on the Lake of Norcia (also known today as the 'Lakes of Pilatus'), is published in its original version, taken from the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786), a copy written by a scribe, Julianus de Campis, in year 1399. Yet, Berchorius' text is much older, as it was probably written in 1335.

¹ Released on February, March, 12th, 16th and 22nd 2018
(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_LegendOrigin.asp)

We find ourselves before the most ancient piece of evidence that is currently available as to the dark legend that enshrouds the Lakes of Pilatus, deeply set beneath the glacial circle formed by the frightful peaks of Mount Vettore, a few miles away from Mount Sibyl, in Italy. A piece of evidence that was written more than a century earlier than Antoine de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", which also mentions the sinister lake.

Fig. 1 - A view of the Lakes of Pilatus in the Sibillini Mountain Range (central Italy)

And this piece of evidence is impressively significant.

«He actually said to me», says Petrus Berchorius, at Book XIV, Chapter 30 "About Italy", as he reports the story that he had once been told, «that amid the peaks which raise near that town there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them; today, no men but necromancers can get to the lake withouth being killed by the demons. Because of that, walls were built around the shore of the lake, and

watched over by guards, lest necromancers be allowed to access the place to consecrate their books to the demons».

[In the original Latin text: «Dicebat enim inter montes isti civitati proximos esse lacum ab antiquis daemonibus consecratum et ab ipsis sensibilibus inhabitatum, ad quem nullus hodie praeter necromanticos potest accedere, quin a daemonibus occidat. Igitur circa terminos lacus facti sunt muri qui a custodibus servantur, ne necromantici pro liberis suis consecrandis daemonibus illuc accedere permittantur»].

Fig. 2 - The excerpt on the Lake of Norcia taken from the “Reductorium Morale” by Petrus Berchorius (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786)

Thus, the earliest text we have about the Lakes of Pilatus, written as early as the first half of the fourteenth century, does not convey the slightest reference to the name of Pontius Pilate and the legend connected to the burial of the body of the Roman prefect of Judaea into the Italian lake, as in later literary works, such as Antoine de la Sale's. Instead, it provides a most

important confirmation: the lake was a place used to practice necromancy, because demons lived in there. And that was known since antiquity.

This is a strong confirmation of a theory we are currently starting to conceive, which will be set out in future comprehensive articles: there is a legendary core in the myth of the Sibyl's cave and lake, which is veiled by a number of superimposed layers of both literary and popular origin, which nothing have to do with the inner nucleus of the legend.

This nucleus is closely linked to the dark renown we find in Petrus Berchorius' account and other literary sources as well.

A dark renown that, if we continue with our perusal of Berchorius' manuscript, grows darker and darker. For a tribute seems to be requested by the fiendish beings who dwell beneath the icy waters of the lake of Norcia.

A tribute to be paid in the form of human lives. As we will see in the next paragraph.

Fig. 3 - The Lakes of Pilatus sitting in the glacial circle of Mount Vettore in winter

2. «Norica» or «Norcia»?

The Lakes of Pilatus, once called the Lake of Norcia, are portrayed with a dark hue in a fourteenth-century text written by a benedictine monk, Petrus Berchorius. The lake, sitting deep in its rocky nest surmounted by the frightful peaks of Mount Vettore, in central Italy, is described as a sinister place, where necromancers used to summon fiendish entities and perform ritual to consecrate their spellbooks.

However, for more than a century, a doubt has troubled the minds of many scholars who have been considering this ancient account: was Berchorius' excerpt truly referring to Norcia? Or, was it pointing to another region, in Italy or elsewhere?

The indecision originated in 1893, with the work of Arturo Graf, an Italian scholar who investigated the tales, symbols and traditions of medieval times. In his “Myths, legends and superstitions of Middle Ages”, Graf publishes, for the first time and to the benefit of modern literary scholars, the Latin text written by Berchorius, together with its Italian translation. It is clear to him that the excerpt is connected to today's Lakes of Pilatus, not far from the town of Norcia; however, the original text available to him reads «Noricam» and «Norica», rather than «Norciam» and «Norcia».

Fig. 4 - Arturo Graf's essay on the Lakes of Pilatus included in his work on the Middle Ages

So, Graf is forced to add a footnote, in which he states the following: «In the printed version I have in my hands in this very moment, I read - a manifest error - “Noricam”. It is not improbable that Bersuire actually wrote "Norciam" instead of "Nursiam", making way to such incorrect spelling» (see figure). A reasonable conjecture on Graf's part, as the ancient territory of “Noricum” is situated in Austria and so Berchorius would have had no reason to include it as a topic in the chapter dedicated to Italy. Nor would the benedictine monk refer to that region as an «Italian town».

Fig. 5 - The assumption proposed by Arturo Graf on the possible misspelling of the word “Norcia”

Was Arturo Graf's assumption true? Was he right? Is Berchorius really talking about a lake placed not in the region of Noricum, but by the town of Norcia?

During the last one hundred twenty-five years, the above doubt has never been properly cleaned up: all the scholars who, in later times, have mentioned Berchorius' words (Luigi Paolucci, 1967; Giuseppe Santarelli, 1974; all the subsequent researchers and writers) just limited their insight effort to a mere quote from the work by Graf, therefore adding nothing to the solution of this critical issue.

Today, “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is proud to confirm that Arturo Graf, in 1893, was totally right. The learned Italian scholar actually made the correct guess.

As the nineteenth-century Italian man of letter writes in his footnote, he was considering a printed version of the “Reductorium Morale”. Just like the one we present in the following figure: a precious printed edition published in Venice in 1583.

Fig. 6 - The 1583 printed edition of the “Reductorium Morale”

In the printed edition, Berchorius text reads as follows: «Exemplum terribile esse circa Noricam Italiae civitatem...». In the original manuscripted version, the same text reads a different way: «Exemplum terribile esse circa Norciam Italie civitatem...» (see figure).

And the same substitution is encountered a few lines below: «a Norica civitate» in the 1583 version, «a Norcia civitate» in the original manuscripted version.

Fig. 7 - A comparison between the printed and manuscripted versions of the “Reductorium Morale”

At last, no doubt remains: the surmise made by Arturo Graf was absolutely correct. Petrus Berchorius is reporting information about a lake, which is not in the Noricum, but in Norcia. A lake that we know today as the Lakes of Pilatus.

But let's continue our analysis of Berchorius' text. We are going to publish, for the first time ever, not only the first portion already quoted by Graf from the “Reductorium Morale” in 1893, but also the second part of the text written in the fourteenth century by the benedictine abbot: nobody has ever seen it before, and “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is thrilled to offer the previously-unknown additional sentences to the attention of today's scholars. In the next paragraph.

3. Ritual offerings in the waters of the Lake of Norcia?

In 1335, a benedictine monk, Petrus Berchorius, provides the first known mention of a lake lying in the vicinity of Norcia, in the Sibillini Range, a mountain ridge in the Italian Apennines. A mention which is very close to the true core of the legendary tale that enshrouds what we know today as the Lakes of Pilatus, and was known in earlier times as the Lake of the Sibyl, or the Lake of Norcia.

Fig. 8 - The Lakes of Pilatus in the shine of a quiet dawn

But Berchorius never writes the words “Pilatus” or “Sibyl”. He goes straight to the inner nucleus of the lake's myth. And this nucleus is definitely dark:

«And about that lake the most horrifying thing is what follows: each year that town [Norcia] sends a single man, a living man, beyond the walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man; and people say that if the town does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms».

Fig. 9 - The subsequent portion of Berchorius' text on the Lake of Norcia in the “Reductorium Morale”

[In the original Latin text: «Est ergo istud ibi summe terribile, quia civitas illa omni anno unum hominem vivum pro tributo infra ambitum murorum iuxta lacum ad daemones mittunt, qui statim visibiliter illum hominem lacerant et consumunt, quod (ut aiunt) si civitas non facit, patria tempestatibus deperiret»].

According to Berchorius, Norcia had the habit to sacrifice a human life in the lake nested beneath the cliffs of Mount Vettore, to appease some kind of demons which would reside in the lake itself - demons that would ravage the whole region if not annually fed with the soul of a man.

Just an unfounded tale? A mere lie which Berchorius had some special, unknown reason to spread around, by including a mention of a heinous conduct in his work?

Actually, we will see that no evidence of such a barbaric and inhuman practice exists at all in any known chronicle reporting details on the ancient history of Norcia. Yet, we will also see that this peculiar topic seems to be recurrent in the tales specifically referred to the Lakes of Pilatus and Mount Sibyl.

But let's proceed with the words written by Berchorius, who further elaborates on the subject:

«Every year the town selects a certain criminal, and sends him there to the demons as a tribute. I would never believe in such a tale, for I could not read anything about such a practice in any books, unless I hadn't heard myself so illustrious a bishop firmly report this account».

[In the original Latin text: «Civitas ergo annuatim aliquem sceleratum eligit que pro tributo daemonibus illuc mittit. Istud autem quia alicubi non legi, nullatenus crederem, nisi a tanto episcopo firmiter asseri audivissem»].

Honestly enough, Petrus Berchorius just confirms his readers that no official account on the history of Norcia has ever provided any reference about such a horrible custom. However, some actual truth seems to be concealed beneath that ghastly rumor, which is reported to him by an unidentified trustworthy clergyman.

Is that all? No. “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is proud to present the additional words spent by Berchorius on this strange hearsay. We are going to report to the contemporary readers the subsequent sentences written by the benedictine abbot on the Lake of Norcia. Words that, at all appearances, have never been reported before, as they were omitted in Arturo Graf's nineteenth-century essay of medieval legends.

For the sake of completeness, we advise the reader that our English rendering of Berchorius' words is not perfect, as the original text contains a number of scribal abbreviations which make it difficult to understand the meaning of each single word written on parchment. For additional help, we refer to the 1583 printed edition, which seems to bear the very same text, with minor variations.

Fig. 10 - The full text on the Lake of Norcia taken from the 1583 printed edition of Petrus Berchorius' “Reductorium Morale”

So let's try to decode the lines that follow in Berchorius' excerpt, as we progress beyond the sentences which we have already reported:

«We may say, if you want, from a symbolic point of view, that this lake means Hell, namely a place and a lake assigned to demons, to which lake no one can get without being consumed by them. For this reason protecting walls were built and guarded by enforcers of the laws of God, that is to say by priests and preachers, lest men are not ruined because of wickedness. This is made to prevent, so people say, that any living men might perish coming from the town of Norcia, and in this way be required as a tribute,

and mainly criminals (?) and damned souls (?) who descend alive into Hell».

[In the original Latin text: «Dic si vis allegorice quod iste lacus significat infernum, qui est locus et lacus demonibus deputatus quo nullus accedit quin sit a demonib. devoratus, et ideo murus mandatorum Dei cum custodibus, i. cum praelatis et praedicatoribus ponitur ad impedimentum [?] ne illuc homines p vitia dilabantur. Iste est ergo lacus quin homines vivos, i. aias q mori nequeunt a Norcia civitate, i. ab isto modo pro tributo appetit re petit (?), quos (?) maxime sceleratos mundus continue sibi mittit et damnandorum animas sibi solvit psal Descendunt in infernum viventes»].

This is the ancient, appalling renown of the Lakes of Pilatus, formerly known as the Lake of Norcia: a place where, according to Berchorius, living men were offered in a ritual killing to unspecified demons so as to propitiate them and avoid an impending destruction. Subsequently, walls were built to prevent such ghastly custom.

We will see, in further articles, that references to this sort of gloomy representation reappear again and again in other antique excerpts, with or without an accompanying reference to Pontius Pilate or an Apennine Sibyl.

What is the meaning of all that? What is Petrus Berchorius talking about? Did really men ever meet a deadly doom into the frosty waters of the Lakes of Pilatus, high amid the cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range? Why no other source on the history of Norcia seems to contain any reference to such a barbaric practice? Can we trace any other ancient text which mentions anything that might remind to us the words written by Berchorius?

The one thing we know at the present stage of our search is that it appears that we are approaching, with uneasy, reluctant steps, the sinister core of the corpus of legendary tales that ominously enshroud the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy, with its lakes and caves and Sibyls. A sinister core we will try to unveil through further studies, which we will present in articles still to come.

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